

Knowledge, awareness and practice of menstrual hygiene and attitude towards menstruation in rural area

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Background:- In Indian society, menstruation is usually regarded as impure. A negative attitude towards this condition has been perpetuated by the isolation of menstruating girls and the limitations placed on them in the household. Women continue to be unaware of the scientific facts and sanitary health practices, which can occasionally have a negative impact on their health, because menstruation and menstrual practices remain shrouded in taboos and socio-cultural constraints. During menstruation, it is crucial to practise good hygiene habits including using sanitary pads and washing the vaginal area thoroughly.

Objectives:- To assess awareness, knowledge, practice of menstrual hygiene and attitude towards menstruation in women of rural area.

Methods:-A community based cross sectional study was conducted at rural based tertiary care hospital. The present study was conducted among women of age group 20-50 years after taking consent from participants. A predesigned and structured questionnaire was used in the study. Personal interviews with the study participants served as the method for gathering data.

Results:-It was evident that 69.7% participants were aware about menstruation before menarche. The most common source of information for 53.5 % participants regarding menstruation were mothers. Only 24.6% of participants use sanitary pads.

Conclusion:- Menstrual hygiene education for women is essential because it reduces the incidence of reproductive tract infections. The critical message of proper menstrual hygiene can be communicated to the women today through educational television programming, qualified school nurses/health staff, motivated school instructors, and informed parents.

Introduction:-

Every month, more than 350 million women and girls in India are ashamed ,uncomfortable and often unsafe.⁽¹⁾ Though the ceremonial focus on "coming of age" is prominent, very little information is provided regarding the real facts of menstruation. A large portion of the knowledge is presented in the form of limitations and restrictions.⁽²⁾ Managing menstruation is linked to embracing womanhood from the moment of menarche and implementing hygiene measures. To reduce menstruation anxiety in girls, all beliefs and taboos that include not taking a bath, avoiding hot and cold meals and not exercising, need to be dispelled because they lack scientific backing. Menstruation is a natural

developmental process that should be explained to teenage girls before menarche so they can accept it and learn how to deal with it.⁽³⁾

In terms of both their social standing and health, teenage females make up a vulnerable demographic. In practically all societies around the world, menstruation is associated with a cultural taboo. Menstruation is linked to numerous unfavorable attitudes in young girls, despite it being a natural occurrence. Reproductive tract infections (RTIs) are less common when proper menstrual cleanliness is followed. The usage of ash, which jeopardizes menstruation hygiene and has long-term effects on women reproductive health, and the recycling of old clothing as pads are two examples of

prevalent, unsanitary traditional practices. Hence, the effects of RTI are serious and can have a detrimental influence on a woman's health, including persistent pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea and in severe cases infertility.

The various schools of thoughts that exist both at home and in the outside world are perceived as trapping and confusing the younger people. This suggests that there is a pressing need to learn more about girls' menstrual requirements, develop appropriate answers, and teach them about the proper techniques for menstruation hygiene, attitudes, and behaviors.⁽⁴⁾ India is a nation of extremes: extreme wealth, extreme poverty and gender-related inequities. As a result, social and health indicators among women and girls vary significantly.⁽⁵⁾

Empirical data indicates that 68 million of the 113 million teenage females attend roughly 1.4 million schools; cultural taboos and subpar menstrual hygiene management practices are cited as barriers to these girls' school attendance.^(6,7,8)

The Indian government is currently working in this area. The menstrual hygiene initiative was introduced in 2011, and as a result, front-line workers are paid incentives to educate and mobilise teenagers on menstruation cleanliness and the usage of sanitary products.

In cooperation with the community health and sanitation council, they also support the installation of toilets in households and ensure that girls have separate, cleaner restrooms in schools.

Adolescent girls' access to the proper knowledge has been impeded by social prohibitions and parents' negative attitudes towards open discussion of connected matters, particularly in rural and tribal communities.⁽⁹⁾ Numerous investigations have shown that the majority of teenage girls lacked or misunderstood basic knowledge regarding menstruation physiology and hygiene. Additionally, it was discovered that the primary sources of information on menstruation that the

teenage girls received were their mothers, television, friends, teachers, and relatives.^(9,10,11)

Aims and objectives:- To assess awareness, knowledge, practice of menstrual hygiene and attitude towards menstruation in women of rural area.

Materials and methods:- A community based cross sectional study was conducted at rural based tertiary care hospital. The present study was conducted among women of age group 20-50 years after taking consent from participants. The study period was done for a period of three months. The study protocol was presented before the institutional ethical committee and consent was obtained.

A predesigned and structured questionnaire was used in the study. After reviewing relevant literature, questionnaires were adopted and modified. Personal interviews with the study participants served as the method for gathering data.

Data was entered in Microsoft excel sheet systematically. Categorical data was analysed. Statistics was taken out in percentages for all variables.

Results:- A total of 455 women were included in the study.

Table No. 1 :-Sociodemographic details of participants.

	No. of women	Percentage
Age group(in years)		
20-30	132	29.8
31-40	266	58.4
41-50	57	11.8
Socioeconomic status		
Above poverty line	162	35.5
Below poverty line	293	64.5
Education		
Illiterate	21	4.5
Primary	273	60

education		
Secondary education	125	27.5
Graduation	36	8

Table No.1:-Out of the total 455 participants 29.8% belonged to the age group of 20-30 years,maximum number of participants belonged to the age group between 31-40 years and the remaining 11.8% belonged to the age group of 41-50 years.Participants belonging to above poverty line were 35.5% while that belonging to below poverty line was 64.5%.From 455 participants 4.5% belonged to the illiterate class while people with primary and secondary education were 60% and 27.5%,only 8% of the total women were graduates.

Table No.2:-Menstrual hygiene practices

Menstrual Hygiene Practices	No. of women	Percentage
Use of material during menstruation		
Sanitary pad	111	24.6
New cloth	315	69.3
Old cloth	28	6.1
Frequency of change of absorbent		
One time per day	177	39.1
Two times per day	192	42
Three times per day	73	16
>3 times per day	13	2.9
Method of disposal of absorbent		
Burn	247	54.5
Dispose it along with routine waste	182	40
Flush/Bury	26	5.5
Incase of		

reusable cloth, it is washed with		
Water and soap	361	79.3
water and antiseptic solution	94	20.7
Cleaning of external genitalia		
One time per day	325	71.5
>1 time per day	130	28.5
Material used to clean external genitalia		
Only water	205	45.4
Soap and water	230	50.4
Water and antiseptic solution	20	4.2

Table No.2:-Only 24.6% of the participants had access to sanitary pads,69.3% used new clothes while 6.1% of the total studied population is still reusing old cloth pads.Frequency of changing the absorbent was once per day was 39.1%,two times per day was 42%, three times per day was 16% and more than three times per day was 2.9%.Majority of the studied participants that used burning as a method to dispose the absorbent was 54.5%,those who disposed it with routine waste accounted for 40% and 5.5% used burying or flushing as a method of disposal.Participants reusing the cloth after washing it with soap and water were 79.3% while disinfecting it with water and antiseptic solution were 20.7%.Cleaning of external genitalia once per day was 71.5% while more than one time per day was 28.5%.Participants using only water to clean their external genitalia were 45.4% while those using water and soap were 50.4% and participants who used water and antiseptic solution were 4.2%.

Table No. 3:-Knowledge about menstruation

Knowledge about menstruation	No. of women	Percentage
Before menarche	317	69.7
After menarche	138	30.3
Source of information about menstruation before menarche		
Mother	243	53.5
School teacher	105	23.2
Friend	54	11.9
Relatives	41	9.1
TV advertisements	12	2.3

Table No.3:- 69.7% of the total 455 participants were aware about menstruation before menarche while 30.35 learned about menstruation after menarche. The source of information about menstruation before menarche were mothers for majority of participants i.e. 53.5%, school teachers accounted for 23.2% in providing information regarding menstruation before menarche, friends accounted for 11.9%, relatives for 9.1% and through TV advertisements was 2.3%.

Table No. 4:-Restrictions during menstruation

Type of restriction	No. of women	Percentage
Do not enter temple/attend puja/ read Quran/enter church	450	98.7
Do not enter kitchen	224	49.1
Do not attend family functions/social gatherings	256	56.3
Stay segregated from family members	181	39.8
Skip school/college/office/	226	49.6

work		
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Table No. 4:-98.7% of participants were restricted from entering temples, attending pujas, reading Quran and entering churches. 49.1% participants refrained from entering the kitchen and 56.3% did not attend family functions/social gatherings. 39.8% stayed segregated from their family and resided in a separate room during the course of menstruation. 49.6% of total studied population skipped school, college, office and work.

Discussion:- Many studies on menstrual hygiene practices have been conducted, however the majority of them focus on schoolgirls or the rural population. This study revealed that age of most of menstruating women lies in the age group of 31-40 years in this area. In a study conducted by Subhash B Thakre et al, majority of menstruating women lied in age group of 12-17 years (12). In our study majority of the population has had access to primary education, which is in accordance to study conducted by Subhash B Thakre et al, which is 60%. The percentage of studied population who has had secondary education is 27.5% which is less as compared to study conducted by Subhash B Thakre et al. (12)

Women's cleanliness habits during their periods are very important since they increase their susceptibility to infections, particularly those of the perineum and urinary system, which can have a negative impact on their health. Reports from studies conducted in developing nations, such as India, have brought attention to the prevalent habits among teenage girls. The kind of absorbent material that is used is crucial since, if it is not cleaned and maintained properly, using it again could lead to infection (11,13). This study revealed that most of the women i.e. 69.3% participating in this study used new cloth

as absorbent during menstruation. In the study conducted by Shanbag *et al* it was seen that during menstruation, 34.7% of the study population used cloth, 44.1% used sanitary pad⁽¹⁴⁾, in our study only 24.6% of studied population used sanitary pads. The research population appears to have been discouraged from utilising the menstrual absorbents on the market by poverty, the high cost of disposable sanitary pads, and to some extent illiteracy.

Cleaning of external genitalia was found to be satisfactory i.e more than two times per day in 28.5% of the studied population, majority of the studied population has unsatisfactory cleaning of vagina during menstruation. Majority of studied population i.e 50.4% used soap and water to clean the external genitalia followed by only water i.e 45.4%, very few i.e only 4.2% population used water and antiseptic solution for cleaning external genitalia. These results were in accordance to study conducted by Subhash B Thakre *et al*⁽¹²⁾. Frequency of change of absorbent was once per day in 39.1% of studied population, two times per day in 42 % of studied population, three times per day in 16% of studied population, these results are in accordance with the results of study conducted by Dhara J Prajapati *et al*⁽¹⁵⁾. Out of the total studied population which reused cloth, 79.3% of them used water and soap to clean the cloth while very few had proper knowledge about disinfectants and used antiseptic solution and water to disinfect the cloth. These results are similar to study conducted by Pramodha S *et al*⁽¹⁶⁾. Method of disposal was found to be burning in majority of studied population i.e 54.5% while 40.0% disposed it in routine waste and 5.5 % disposed it by flushing in toilets, these results are similar with the study conducted by Subhash B Thakre *et al*⁽¹²⁾.

In our studied population 69.7% of women had knowledge about menstruation before menarche and 30.3% had learnt at

menarche. In a similar study conducted by A Dasgupta *et al* 67.5% had knowledge about menstruation during menarche. In our study the most common informant about menstruation before menarche were mothers i.e 53.5%, followed by school teachers to be 23.2%, friends 11.9%, relatives 9.1%. T.V advertisements also played role in providing information regarding menstruation. This data is similar to study conducted by A Dasgupta *et al*⁽¹¹⁾.

In Indian households menstruation has been stigmatised since time immemorial since it originates from the concept of purity versus pollution which is practiced in all the religions. Menstruating women are considered as impure and various restrictions in the form of not being allowed to attend religious gatherings, reading holy scriptures, perform daily puja/prayers, entering kitchen and social gatherings are imposed on them. The most common form of restriction practiced is not attending pujas, reading Qurans and attending churches, this was seen in 98.7% of studied population. Girls are expected to skip schools, offices and stay segregated in their own homes. This was also seen in our studied population. Women skipping schools and offices accounted to 49.6%, women staying segregated in their own households are around 39.8%. In a study conducted by Purva Shoor *et al* also showed that 39% of women stayed segregated in their homes and 25% do not enter kitchens.⁽¹⁷⁾

Conclusion:- This study has highlighted the need for proper menstrual training in the society where girls need to be educated about menstruation and menstrual hygiene from an early age so that they can practice correct methods of maintaining hygiene during menstruation and also to help them overcome the taboos associated with menstruation which have been inculcated in the Indian society since generations. For the dissemination of information about

menstruation, formal as well as informal avenues of communication such as mothers, sisters, and friends must be prioritised. Given the crucial role that mothers play, it is imperative that they possess accurate and pertinent information regarding reproductive health, enabling them to impart this knowledge to their developing daughter.

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